

Public use of ChatGPT for medication information in Saudi Arabia: a cross-sectional study

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Received 7 November 2025 ♦ Accepted 5 March 2026 ♦ Published 25 March 2026

Citation: Alhomoud F (2026) Public use of ChatGPT for medication information in Saudi Arabia: a cross-sectional study. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e177347>

Abstract

A cross-sectional online survey was conducted among adults in Saudi Arabia to explore public use of ChatGPT for medication-related information. A validated, self-administered questionnaire was distributed through social media platforms and analyzed using descriptive statistics and binary logistic regression. Among 475 respondents, nearly two-thirds reported using ChatGPT to inquire about medication use, mechanisms of action, and side effects. About one-third modified their medication behavior, raising potential safety concerns. ChatGPT use was more common among older adults, individuals with diploma-level education, those who were employed, unemployed, or retired, and participants living in smaller households. In contrast, participants working in medical professions, those earning less than 8,000 SAR per month, and users of over-the-counter or herbal products were less likely to use ChatGPT. Speed, accessibility, and ease of use were key facilitators, whereas doubts about accuracy and preference for healthcare professionals remained barriers. The findings indicate growing reliance on ChatGPT for medication information and suggest the need for public education, AI literacy, and stronger regulatory oversight.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, drug information services, information-seeking behavior, perception

Introduction

Since its release in 2022, Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer (ChatGPT)—a freely accessible artificial intelligence (AI) chatbot—has increasingly been used as a source of health- and medication-related information, providing instant, human-like responses to diverse queries (Vallance 2022; Temsah et al. 2023). Its widespread adoption has been driven by accessibility and convenience, as well as the ability to obtain personalized information without direct interaction with healthcare professionals (Hu 2023; Ayre et al. 2025). The need for timely digital

health information has grown considerably following the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly in Saudi Arabia, where the expansion of virtual healthcare services and pressure on government-funded healthcare systems have led many individuals to seek alternative sources of rapid guidance, including AI-based platforms such as ChatGPT (Shanafelt and Ripp 2022; Sinsky et al. 2022; Alhur et al. 2023; Aldekhyyel et al. 2024; Alharbi et al. 2024; Syed et al. 2024).

Despite its convenience, concerns persist about the accuracy, reliability, and safety of ChatGPT's health-related responses (Cheng et al. 2022; Beavers et al. 2023; Lee et al. 2023; Morath et al. 2023; Fournier et al. 2024; Mu and

He 2024; Wei et al. 2024; Wu and Zhang, 2024; Yousif et al. 2024; Beheshti et al. 2025). Generative AI tools are also used for symptom checking, treatment suggestions, and medication guidance; however, inappropriate reliance on AI-generated advice—such as modifying medication doses, initiating treatments without professional consultation, or overlooking drug–drug interactions—may result in misinformation, unsafe practices, and diminished public trust (Battineni et al. 2020; Duwe et al. 2024; Schukow et al. 2024). Moreover, the confident, authoritative tone of AI-generated responses may further increase the risk that users accept incorrect information without verification.

Several studies assessing ChatGPT's responses on medication-related topics have identified significant accuracy issues. One study reported that only 26% of 39 responses were satisfactory in accuracy and completeness, while others contained errors or fabricated references (Lee et al. 2023). Another found an overall accuracy of 44.9% across 69 questions (Fournier et al. 2024), and a third noted that most of the 50 drug-related replies were partly or wholly inaccurate (Morath et al. 2023). These results emphasize the need for cautious use of ChatGPT for medication information and for understanding how patients and healthcare professionals interact with such tools to ensure safe and equitable access to reliable information (Battineni et al. 2020; Beavers et al. 2023; Lee et al. 2023; Morath et al. 2023; Fournier et al. 2024; Duwe et al. 2024; Schukow et al. 2024; Wei et al. 2024; Wu and Zhang 2024; Beheshti et al. 2025).

As awareness and use of AI technologies continue to grow, engagement with ChatGPT for health and medication information is expected to increase (Panch et al. 2019; Alhur et al. 2023; Temsah et al. 2023; Syed et al. 2024; Alanezi 2024; Alharbi et al. 2024; Shahsavar and Choudhury 2023; Sobaih et al. 2024). In Saudi Arabia, where digital health literacy is rapidly expanding, understanding public use of AI-based medication information sources is essential for informing policy, regulation, and educational interventions. However, evidence on how the Saudi public uses ChatGPT for medication-related inquiries remains limited. Therefore, this study aims to examine the prevalence, usage patterns, perceived benefits, barriers, and potential risks associated with using ChatGPT for medication information among the Saudi public.

Materials and methods

Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted using an online survey.

Setting, samples, recruitment, and data collection method

The survey was hosted on an online platform (QuestionPro, Austin, Texas, USA) and distributed over 2 months through various social media channels, including X

(formerly Twitter), Facebook, LinkedIn, and WhatsApp. Participants were recruited using a convenience sampling strategy, whereby the survey link was shared publicly, allowing individuals who met the inclusion criteria to self-select into the study. Eligible participants included adults aged 18 years or older who were proficient in Arabic or English and resided in Saudi Arabia.

The survey was designed to take 5–10 minutes to complete. To prevent duplicate submissions, the “Prevent Ballot Box Stuffing” feature in QuestionPro was activated. Additionally, the survey required participants to answer all questions, and only fully completed responses (100% completion) were included in the final analysis. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles set out in the Declaration of Helsinki. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the confidentiality of their responses, and the voluntary nature of their participation, including their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Written consent was obtained before administering the questionnaire, and participants were assured that their data would be used solely for research purposes.

Sample size

The required sample size for this study was calculated using the Raosoft online sample size calculator (Raosoft Inc. 2004), applying a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Assuming a 50% response rate and a target population of 34,566,328 adults aged 18 and above in Saudi Arabia (Worldometer 2025), the minimum sample size was estimated at approximately 385 participants.

Survey tool development, translation, and validation

The author developed the questionnaire based on relevant literature and previously validated instruments, including studies on similar topics (Crilly et al. 2019; Valdez et al. 2021; Shahsavar and Choudhury 2023; Ayre et al. 2025). The questionnaire consisted of 48 questions organized into eight main sections. The first section (11 questions) collected participants' demographic information, including gender, age, education level, employment status, residence, and household characteristics. The second section (five questions) focused on the current use of medications, including both prescribed and over-the-counter medications. The third section (two questions) assessed participants' awareness of ChatGPT. The fourth section (two questions) examined the usage patterns of ChatGPT, specifically for medication-related queries. The fifth section (four questions) investigated behavioral changes resulting from ChatGPT's advice, including any adverse outcomes. The sixth section (two questions) assessed levels of trust and satisfaction with ChatGPT's medication-related information. The seventh section (two questions) explored reasons for using or not using ChatGPT for this type of information. The eighth and final section (two questions)

examined future intentions and motivations for using ChatGPT regarding medications.

The questionnaire included multiple-choice, closed-ended questions that allowed participants to select one or more applicable responses. For some items, total response percentages exceeded 100% due to multiple selections. An “Other” option was included where relevant to allow for additional input. Participants were also asked to indicate their level of agreement or perception regarding trust and satisfaction using Likert-type scales (e.g., from “Not at all” to “Completely”).

To enhance content validity, the draft instrument was reviewed by three expert pharmacists who evaluated its clarity, relevance, comprehensiveness, and cultural appropriateness. Minor modifications were made in response to their feedback. The revised version was pilot-tested with five individuals from the target population who were not involved in the main study to assess face validity and ensure comprehensibility. Their feedback confirmed that the questions were understandable and appropriate, with no major modifications required.

The original English version of the questionnaire was translated into Arabic using the parallel translation method (Valdez et al. 2021), in which two bilingual researchers independently translated the content. Both translators were fluent in English, native Arabic speakers, and experienced in health-related research and interviewing. Their translations were compared, and any discrepancies were discussed and resolved before the Arabic version was finalized. To further assess face validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by two pharmacists fluent in both English and Arabic; neither suggested major changes. Additionally, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with two native Arabic speakers to evaluate clarity, comprehension, and content, and no significant revisions were recommended.

Ethical consideration

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, Saudi Arabia, and adhered to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Prior to data collection, IRB approval was obtained. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained electronically prior to the start of the online survey. Participants were informed about the study’s objectives, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. No identifying personal information was collected, and all responses were kept confidential and stored securely for research purposes only.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 29 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participants’ baseline characteristics, presented as counts

and percentages for categorical variables. In the bivariate analysis, a chi-square test (χ^2) was performed to examine the association between participants’ use of ChatGPT for medication-related inquiries (yes/no) and their characteristics and medication use patterns. Chi-square (χ^2) values, degrees of freedom (df), and *p*-values were reported.

A multiple logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify demographic and medication-related factors independently associated with participants’ use of ChatGPT for medication-related inquiries. Odds ratios (ORs) and their corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported. All *p*-values were two-tailed, and a *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant in the analysis.

Results

Participant characteristics

A total of 475 respondents completed the survey. The majority were female (69.26%), mainly aged 25–44 years (47.79%), and Saudi nationals (93.05%), with most residing in the Eastern Province (75.58%). Over half were employed (full-time, part-time, or self-employed) (57.3%), and 55.87% held a bachelor’s degree. Approximately 57.5% of respondents did not have a medical background, 52.63% had private health insurance, and 64.42% reported having a family member who was a healthcare provider. Approximately half of the participants (48.84%) lived in households of 4–6 members. Nearly one-third (28%) earned less than 8,000 SAR per month. A full description of participants’ characteristics is provided in Table 1.

Medication use patterns

Just under half of participants (221/475, 46.5%) were taking at least one regularly prescribed medication. Among these, the most frequently reported conditions were high blood pressure (11.7%), high cholesterol (10.9%), allergies (10.1%), skin conditions (9.8%), thyroid disorders (7.7%), and diabetes (7.4%). Among prescription users, the majority (192/221, 86.9%) reported taking 1–3 medications. In addition, two-thirds of respondents (318/475, 67.0%) reported using non-prescription products, including over-the-counter medications, vitamins, supplements, or herbal remedies. When asked about their ability to read and understand medication information, 34.1% (162/475) said they rarely needed help, and 31.4% (148/475) said they sometimes required assistance. Detailed results on medication use patterns are presented in Table 2.

Awareness and use of ChatGPT

Almost all participants (462/475, 97.26%) had heard of ChatGPT or similar AI chatbots, and 65.05% (309/475) had used it for medication-related questions within the past 12 months. Among users (*n* = 309), ChatGPT was most commonly consulted monthly (95/309, 30.74%), weekly

Table 1. Characteristics of participants recruited into the study (total number = 475).

Variable	N	%
Gender		
Male	146	30.47%
Female	329	69.26%
Age		
18–24	126	26.53%
25–44	227	47.79%
45 and above	122	25.68%
Nationality		
Saudi	442	93.05%
Non-Saudi	33	6.95%
Level of education		
High school or below	72	15.2%
A diploma degree	37	7.8%
Bachelor's degree	265	55.87%
Postgraduate studies (Master's or Ph.D.)	101	21.3%
Employment status		
Employed (full-time, part-time, or self-employed)	272	57.3%
Unemployed	72	15.2%
Retired	30	6.3%
Student	101	21.3%
Profession		
Medical profession/qualification	202	42.5%
Non-medical profession/qualification	273	57.5%
Income per month		
No income	105	22.11%
< 8,000 SAR	133	28%
8,000–16,000 SAR	131	27.58%
> 16,000 SAR	106	22.32%
Private health insurance		
Yes	250	52.63%
No	225	47.37%
Province		
Eastern province	359	75.58%
Other provinces	116	24.41%
Healthcare provider in the family		
Yes	306	64.42%
No	169	35.58%
Number of people in the house		
1–3	103	21.68%
4–6	232	48.84%
> 6	140	29.47%

N = number; % = percentage; SAR = Saudi Arabian riyal.

(67/309, 21.68%), or every 6 months (64/309, 20.71%). A smaller proportion used it almost daily (45/309, 14.56%) or only once (39/309, 12.3%) during the past year.

The most common queries asked to ChatGPT concerned how to take the medication (13.0%), the mechanism of action (12.8%), and side effects or adverse reactions (11.7%). Other frequently mentioned topics included treatment options or alternatives (9.7%), long-term effects or safety (9.2%), and drug–food or drug–drug interactions (8.1%). Fewer respondents inquired about the use of medication during pregnancy or lactation (4.4%),

medication use in children (4.4%), missed doses (4.7%), the consequences of not taking the medication (4.0%), or storage, disposal, or stability (4.0%). These findings are summarized in Table 3.

Behavioral impact of ChatGPT use

Nearly one-third (96/309, 31.07%) of ChatGPT users reported changing their medication use after receiving information. Because participants were allowed to select more than one type of behavioral change, the total number of reported changes exceeded the number of individuals. A total of 130 behavioral responses were recorded. Among these responses, 44.6% (58/130) involved modifying the dose or timing of an existing medication, 35.4% (46/130) involved starting a new medication or supplement, and 20.0% (26/130) involved stopping a medication altogether.

Of those who changed their behavior, 13.54% (13/96) experienced an unpleasant or unexpected outcome. The most common experiences were feeling anxious or confused (8/21, 38.1%), unexpected side effects (6/21, 28.57%), receiving incorrect or misleading advice (4/21, 19.05%), a worsened health condition (2/21, 9.52%), and one participant (4.76%) had to seek help from a doctor or pharmacist afterward.

Trust and satisfaction

Half of ChatGPT users (156/309, 50.49%) reported moderate trust in its medication advice; 29.77% (92/309) trusted it slightly; 11.33% (35/309) trusted it very much; and only 1.62% (5/309) trusted it completely. Conversely, 6.8% (21/309) expressed no trust at all.

In terms of satisfaction, 131 (42.4%) participants were satisfied, 128 (41.4%) were neutral, and 22 (7.1%) were very satisfied with ChatGPT for medication information. Only 28 (9.1%)—18 (5.8%) dissatisfied and 10 (3.2%) very dissatisfied—reported negative experiences.

Facilitators and barriers

As shown in Table 4, the most frequently cited reasons among users for consulting ChatGPT were its speed in obtaining answers ($n = 269$, 26.6%) and ease of use ($n = 222$, 22.0%), followed by helping users understand medications better ($n = 124$, 12.3%), being free of charge ($n = 112$, 11.1%), and being useful when access to healthcare providers was limited ($n = 64$, 6.3%). Other motivating factors included protection of user privacy ($n = 57$, 5.6%) and access to up-to-date information ($n = 54$, 5.3%), with smaller proportions citing embarrassment to ask health professionals ($n = 49$, 4.9%), trust in ChatGPT's information accuracy ($n = 34$, 3.4%), or recommendations from others ($n = 11$, 1.1%).

Among non-users, the most common barriers were a preference for consulting healthcare professionals ($n = 130$, 43.6%), concerns about incorrect information ($n = 80$, 26.9%), advice from others not to rely on AI tools for medical information ($n = 32$, 10.7%), and concerns

Table 2. Use of medications among participants.

Variable	Category	N	%
Use of regularly prescribed medications (<i>n</i> = 475)	Yes	221	46.53%
	No	254	53.47%
Medical condition for prescribed medications (<i>n</i> = 221)	High blood pressure	43	11.7%
	Asthma	16	4.4%
	Allergy	37	10.1%
	High cholesterol	40	10.9%
	Skin condition	36	9.8%
	Chronic pain	18	4.9%
	Heart condition	6	1.6%
	Psychological and neurological conditions	22	6.0%
	Bone and joint disorders	32	8.7%
	Blood disorders	21	5.7%
	Thyroid gland disorder	28	7.7%
	Diabetes	27	7.4%
	Infection (e.g., bacterial, viral, fungal, and so on)	22	6.0%
	Other (e.g., autoimmune diseases, chronic kidney diseases, or gastrointestinal disorders)	18	4.9%
Number of regular prescription medications (<i>n</i> = 221)	1–3	192	86.88%
	≥ 4	29	13.12%
Use of over-the-counter or herbal medications (<i>n</i> = 475)	Yes	318	66.95%
	No	157	33.05%
Need for assistance with reading or understanding medication information (<i>n</i> = 475)	Never	101	21.26%
	Rarely	162	34.11%
	Sometimes	149	31.37%
	Often	40	8.42%
	Always	23	4.84%

N = number; % = percentage.

Table 3. Types of questions participants asked ChatGPT.

Type of question	N	%
Mechanism of action	162	12.8%
Consequences of not taking the medication	51	4.0%
Treatment options or alternatives	122	9.7%
Consequences of missed doses	59	4.7%
Long-term effects or safety	116	9.2%
Dependency or addiction potential	40	3.2%
How to take the medication (dose, timing, route)	164	13.0%
Storage, disposal, or stability	51	4.0%
Use during pregnancy or lactation	56	4.4%
Medication use in children	55	4.4%
Vaccination-related questions	23	1.8%
Side effects or adverse reactions	148	11.7%
Drug–food or drug–drug interactions	102	8.1%
Cost or availability of the medication	24	1.9%
Over-the-counter or herbal/complementary alternatives	49	3.9%
Need to consult a healthcare professional (pharmacist or doctor)	33	2.6%
Other	6	0.5%

Participants could select more than one option.

about privacy or data security (*n* = 23, 7.7%). Fewer participants reported difficulty using the tool (*n* = 12, 4.0%), lack of reliable internet or suitable devices (*n* = 4, 1.3%), or no need for such services (*n* = 17, 5.7%) (Table 4).

Future intentions

Regarding future use, 60.0% of respondents indicated they were likely to use ChatGPT for medication information in the next year—30.6% definitely and 29.4% probably. In contrast, 40.0% of respondents were uncertain or unlikely to use it—18.3% were unsure, while 21.7% stated they were unlikely or definitely not.

Statistical associations with the use of ChatGPT

Chi-square tests indicated significant associations between ChatGPT use for medication-related information and several characteristics. Significant relationships were observed with age ($p < 0.001$), education level ($p = 0.033$), employment status ($p < 0.001$), profession ($p < 0.001$), household size ($p = 0.007$), and use of over-the-counter or herbal medications ($p = 0.004$).

Younger adults (18–44 years), participants with higher levels of education, those employed in medical professions, and individuals who used non-prescription or herbal medications were more likely to use ChatGPT for medication information. Respondents from smaller households also reported higher usage rates. Regular prescription use showed no significant association ($p = 0.06$) (Table 5).

Table 4. Facilitators and barriers to using ChatGPT for medication-related information.

Facilitators (motivating factors)	N	%	Barriers (inhibiting factors)	N	%
Provides answers more quickly than other sources	269	26.63%	Prefer to get advice from a real person (doctor/pharmacist)	130	43.62%
Easy and convenient to use	222	21.98%	Information may be incorrect	80	26.85%
Helps to understand medication better	124	12.28%	Advised not to rely on AI tools for medical information	32	10.74%
Free of charge	112	11.09%	Concerned about privacy/data security	23	7.72%
Up-to-date information	54	5.35%	Do not know how to use/find it difficult	12	4.03%
Protects user privacy	57	5.64%	No reliable internet/device	4	1.34%
Lack of access to a doctor/pharmacist	64	6.34%	Other reasons (e.g., no need)	17	5.70%
Embarrassed to ask a health professional	49	4.85%			
Information accuracy (trust in ChatGPT)	34	3.37%			
Recommended by others	11	1.09%			
Other reasons (e.g., curiosity)	14	1.39%			

Participants could select more than one option.

Binary logistic regression analysis identified several significant predictors of ChatGPT use for medication-related information. Younger participants were significantly less likely to use ChatGPT than those aged 45 years and above. Specifically, participants aged 18–24 had significantly lower odds of ChatGPT use (OR = 0.101, 95% CI: 0.054–0.187; $p < 0.001$), and those aged 25–44 years also had significantly lower odds (OR = 0.281, 95% CI: 0.177–0.446; $p < 0.001$). Regarding educational attainment, compared with participants with postgraduate education, those with a diploma had significantly higher odds of using ChatGPT (OR = 2.705, 95% CI: 1.250–5.853, $p = 0.012$). However, no significant differences were observed for participants with high school education or below (OR = 1.165, 95% CI: 0.617–2.199, $p = 0.638$) or those with a bachelor's degree (OR = 0.968, 95% CI: 0.607–1.614, $p = 0.968$) compared with the postgraduate group.

Regarding employment status, participants who were employed (OR = 2.470, 95% CI: 1.141–4.310, $p = 0.001$), unemployed (OR = 2.911, 95% CI: 1.466–5.781, $p = 0.002$), and retired (OR = 7.455, 95% CI: 3.047–18.238, $p < 0.001$) had significantly higher odds of using ChatGPT for medication-related information compared with students, who served as the reference group. Profession was also significantly associated with the use of ChatGPT. Individuals working in medical professions were less likely to use ChatGPT than those in non-medical fields (OR = 0.360, 95% CI: 0.239–0.542, $p < 0.001$). Household size was also significantly associated with the use of ChatGPT. Compared with participants living in households with more than six members, those living in households of 1–3 people (OR = 2.147, 95% CI: 1.237–3.724, $p = 0.007$) and 4–6 people (OR = 1.976, 95% CI: 1.238–3.155, $p = 0.004$) had significantly higher odds of using ChatGPT for medication-related information.

Monthly income was also examined in the regression model. Compared with participants earning more than 16,000 SAR per month, those earning less than 8,000 SAR had significantly lower odds of using ChatGPT for medication-related information (OR = 0.564, 95% CI: 0.329–0.966, $p = 0.037$). No significant differences were observed among participants with no income (OR = 0.867, 95% CI:

0.499–1.506, $p = 0.613$) or those earning 8,000–16,000 SAR (OR = 0.713, 95% CI: 0.420–1.211, $p = 0.210$) compared with the highest income group.

Similarly, participants who reported using over-the-counter or herbal medications had significantly lower odds of using ChatGPT for medication-related information compared with those who did not use these products (OR = 0.560, 95% CI: 0.377–0.831, $p = 0.004$).

No significant associations were observed for gender, private health insurance, province, regular prescription use, having a healthcare provider in the family, or the need for assistance with reading or understanding medication information ($p > 0.05$). The final logistic regression model was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 45.86$, $p < 0.001$) and explained approximately 27% of the variance in ChatGPT use (Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.27$), indicating a moderate model fit (Table 6).

Discussion

This study provides novel insights into how the Saudi public uses ChatGPT for medication-related information, revealing considerable engagement with the tool. Nearly two-thirds of participants reported using ChatGPT to ask about medications, most commonly to learn how to take them, understand their mechanisms of action, and identify potential side effects. Similar patterns of AI chatbot use for rapid health information have been reported in international studies. Patient questions commonly focus on drug indications, mechanisms of action, instructions for use, adverse drug reactions, and contraindications (Wang et al. 2023; Andrikyan et al. 2025).

A notable proportion of users (31%) reported modifying their medication behavior based on ChatGPT's information, including changing doses or initiating or discontinuing medications. Although only a minority reported adverse outcomes, this finding suggests potential safety risks. Prior studies evaluating ChatGPT's medication advice found that 44%–74% of responses contained inaccuracies or incomplete information. For instance, Lee et al. (2023) and Fournier et al. (2024) observed that ChatGPT

Table 5. Bivariate associations between participant characteristics, medication use patterns, and use of ChatGPT for medication-related information.

Variable	Used ChatGPT N (%)	Did not use ChatGPT N (%)	X ²	df	P-Value
Gender					
Male	101 (32.7)	45 (27.1)	1.578	1	0.209
Female	208 (67.3)	121 (72.9)			
Age					
18–24	108 (35)	18 (10.8)	64.837	2	< 0.001
25–44	155 (50.2)	72 (43.4)			
45 and above	46 (14.9)	76 (45.8)			
Level of education					
High school or below	46 (14.9)	26 (15.7)	8.739	3	0.033
A diploma degree	16 (5.2)	21 (12.7)			
Bachelor's degree	179 (57.9)	86 (51.8)			
Postgraduate studies (Master's or Ph.D.)	68 (22.0)	33 (19.9)			
Employment status					
Employed (full-time, part-time, self-employed)	173 (56.0)	99 (59.6)	23.351	3	< 0.001
Unemployed	43 (13.9)	29 (17.5)			
Retired	11 (3.6)	19 (11.4)			
Student	82 (26.5)	19 (11.4)			
Profession					
Medical profession	157 (50.8)	45 (27.1)	24.818	1	< 0.001
Non-medical profession	152 (49.2)	121 (72.9)			
Income per month					
No income	65 (21.0)	40 (24.1)	4.950	3	0.175
< 8,000 SAR	95 (30.7)	38 (22.9)			
8,000–16,000 SAR	87 (28.2)	44 (26.5)			
> 16,000 SAR	62 (20.1)	44 (26.5)			
Private health insurance					
Yes	150 (51.8)	90 (54.2)	0.257	1	0.612
No	149 (48.2)	76 (45.8)			
Province					
Eastern province	240 (77.7)	119 (71.7)	2.094	1	0.148
Other provinces	69 (22.3)	47 (28.3)			
Healthcare provider in the family					
Yes	196 (63.4)	110 (66.3)	0.379	1	0.538
No	113 (36.6)	56 (33.7)			
Number of people in the house					
1–3	61 (19.7)	42 (25.3)	10.049	2	0.007
4–6	142 (46.0)	90 (54.2)			
> 6	106 (34.3)	34 (20.5)			
Regular prescription use					
Yes	134 (43.4)	87 (52.4)	3.550	1	0.060
No	175 (56.6)	79 (47.6)			
Number of regular prescription medications					
1–3	118 (88.1)	74 (85.1)	0.417	1	0.518
≥ 4	16 (11.9)	13 (14.9)			
Use of over-the-counter or herbal medications					
Yes	221 (71.5)	97 (58.4)	8.359	1	0.004
No	88 (28.5)	69 (41.6)			
Need for assistance with reading or understanding medication information					
Independent (rarely or never needs help)	165 (53.4)	98 (59.0)	1.389	1	0.239
Needs assistance (sometimes/often/always)	144 (46.6)	68 (41.0)			

χ^2 = chi-square statistic, df = degrees of freedom, p-value = probability value indicating statistical significance.

frequently provided plausible yet incorrect drug information, highlighting the danger of overreliance on AI without professional verification. The present findings therefore reinforce calls for AI literacy and public education on verifying AI-generated health information before acting on it.

Speed, ease of use, and free access were the main facilitators driving ChatGPT use, consistent with previous research on digital health adoption. Users valued its efficiency and privacy—especially when discussing sensitive health concerns—reflecting a culturally contextualized

Table 6. Predictors of ChatGPT use (binary logistic regression analysis).

Parameter	Binary logistic		
	OR (95% CI)	P-value	
Gender	Male	0.766 (0.505–1.162)	0.210
	Female	Reference	
Age	18–24	0.101 (0.054–0.187)	< 0.001
	25–44	0.281 (0.177–0.446)	< 0.001
	45 and above	Reference	
Level of education	High school or below	1.165 (0.617–2.199)	0.638
	A diploma degree	2.705 (1.250–5.853)	0.012
	Bachelor's degree	0.968 (0.607–1.614)	0.968
	Postgraduate studies (Master's or Ph.D.)	Reference	
Employment status	Employed	2.470 (1.141–4.310)	0.001
	Unemployed	2.911 (1.466–5.781)	0.002
	Retired	7.455 (3.047–18.238)	< 0.001
	Student	Reference	
Profession	Medical profession	0.360 (0.239–0.542)	< 0.001
	Non-medical profession	Reference	
Income per month	No income	0.867 (0.499–1.506)	0.613
	< 8,000 SAR	0.564 (0.329–0.966)	0.037
	8,000–16,000 SAR	0.713 (0.420–1.211)	0.210
	> 16,000 SAR	Reference	
Private health insurance	Yes	1.103 (0.756–1.610)	0.612
	No	Reference	
Province	Eastern province	0.728 (0.473–1.120)	0.149
	Other provinces	Reference	
Healthcare provider in the family	Yes	1.132 (0.762–1.683)	0.538
	No	Reference	
Number of people in the house	1–3	2.147 (1.237–3.724)	0.007
	4–6	1.976 (1.238–3.155)	0.004
	> 6	Reference	
Regular prescription use	Yes	1.438 (0.985–2.100)	0.060
	No	Reference	
Number of regular prescription medications	1–3	0.772 (0.351–1.696)	0.519
	≥ 4	Reference	
Use of over-the-counter or herbal medications	Yes	0.560 (0.377–0.831)	0.004
	No	Reference	
Need for assistance with reading or understanding medication information	Independent (rarely or never needs help)	1.258 (0.859–1.842)	0.239
	Needs assistance (sometimes/often/always)	Reference	

OR = odds ratio, CI = confidence interval, *p*-value = probability value indicating statistical significance.

preference in Saudi Arabia, where individuals may avoid seeking direct consultation for certain issues (Alhur et al. 2023; Alanezi et al. 2024; Alharbi et al. 2024; Syed et al. 2024). However, the most frequently cited barriers—preference for consulting healthcare professionals and concerns about incorrect information—indicate that users remain cautious about the reliability of AI (Richardson et al. 2021; Hassan et al. 2024). This pattern is consistent with international studies reporting cautious public engagement with AI-based health tools (Richardson et al. 2021; Hassan et al. 2024).

Trust and satisfaction levels were moderate, suggesting that users appreciate ChatGPT's accessibility but remain uncertain about its credibility. Only 11% reported strong trust, and most users expressed neutral satisfaction. This finding aligns with those of Beheshti et al. (2025) and

Wei et al. (2024), who documented mixed perceptions of ChatGPT's accuracy and safety in health communication. While ChatGPT's linguistic fluency and responsiveness attract users, its lack of accountability and potential for misinformation limit full trust. Continued AI development and integration of verified medical databases may enhance the accuracy and acceptance of such tools in the future.

Regression analysis revealed several demographic and behavioral factors associated with the use of ChatGPT for medication-related information. Interestingly, younger participants were significantly less likely to use ChatGPT than those aged 45 years and older. This finding contrasts with several previous studies reporting greater adoption of AI-based technologies among younger, digitally literate populations (Shahsavari and Choudhury 2023; Jeong and Nam 2024; Esmaeilzadeh et al. 2025). One possible

explanation is that older adults may have greater health-related information needs due to a higher burden of chronic conditions and medication use, prompting them to seek additional sources of information, such as AI chatbots. In Saudi Arabia, increasing digital literacy among older adults and wider access to mobile health technologies may also contribute to their engagement with emerging digital tools (Albinsaad et al. 2024; Alharbi et al. 2024; AlWatban et al. 2024; Syed et al. 2024; Almoajel et al. 2025).

This interpretation is further supported by the regression findings related to medication use. Participants who reported regularly using prescribed medications showed higher odds of ChatGPT use, although this association did not reach statistical significance. While the result should therefore be interpreted with caution, the observed trend may nevertheless reflect greater information-seeking behavior among individuals managing ongoing health conditions. Such individuals may turn to digital tools to better understand their medications, potential side effects, or treatment options, which could partly explain the higher use of ChatGPT observed among older participants.

Regarding education, individuals with a diploma had significantly higher odds of using ChatGPT than those with postgraduate degrees, while no significant differences were observed for participants with high school or bachelor's degrees. This pattern may reflect differences in information-seeking behaviors across educational groups. Individuals with intermediate educational levels may rely more on accessible digital tools such as AI chatbots to obtain health information, whereas those with advanced academic training may prefer traditional evidence-based sources or professional consultation.

Employment status also demonstrated a strong association with ChatGPT use. Compared with students, participants who were employed, unemployed, or retired had significantly higher odds of using ChatGPT for medication-related information. The particularly high odds observed among retired individuals may reflect their increased need for medication-related information and self-management support. Similarly, employed individuals may prefer quick, convenient information sources due to time constraints, while unemployed individuals may have more time to explore digital tools and online resources for health-related inquiries.

Interestingly, participants working in medical professions were significantly less likely to use ChatGPT compared with those in non-medical fields. This finding may reflect greater reliance on formal medical knowledge, professional training, and trusted clinical resources among healthcare professionals. Individuals with medical backgrounds may prefer consulting scientific literature, clinical guidelines, or professional colleagues rather than relying on AI-generated responses, particularly when seeking medication-related information.

Household size was also significantly associated with ChatGPT use. Participants living in smaller households (1–3 or 4–6 members) were more likely to use ChatGPT than those living in households with more than six

members. This may reflect greater reliance on self-directed information sources among individuals living in smaller families, where fewer household members may be available to provide advice or share health-related experiences. Similar patterns have been reported in digital health research, where individuals with limited in-house social support tend to engage more actively with online health information sources (Syed et al. 2024; Almoajel et al. 2025).

Income also played a role in the use of ChatGPT. Participants with monthly incomes below 8,000 SAR were significantly less likely to use ChatGPT compared with those earning more than 16,000 SAR. This finding may reflect socioeconomic differences in access to digital technologies, internet connectivity, and digital literacy. Individuals with higher incomes may have greater access to digital devices and online platforms, which may facilitate the use of emerging AI-based tools for health information.

Finally, participants who reported using over-the-counter or herbal medications were less likely to use ChatGPT for medication-related information compared with those who did not use such products. This may suggest that individuals who frequently use non-prescription products rely more on traditional sources of advice, such as pharmacists, family members, or personal experience, rather than AI-based tools. Alternatively, it may indicate that users of OTC or herbal products already feel confident in their self-care practices and therefore may not perceive the need to consult digital health technologies for additional guidance.

Strengths and limitations of the study

A key strength of this study is its exploration of the use of ChatGPT for medication-related information among the Saudi public—a novel area with limited research. A major strength of this study is its large, diverse sample, which provides valuable real-world insights into public engagement with ChatGPT in Saudi Arabia.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference; associations identified cannot establish directionality between predictors and ChatGPT use. Second, the convenience sampling approach, though practical for online surveys, may have introduced selection bias toward digitally active individuals. Third, self-reported behaviors may be subject to recall or social desirability bias, particularly when discussing sensitive topics such as medication modification without medical consultation. Fourth, the study did not assess the actual accuracy of the ChatGPT responses that participants consulted. Fifth, the use of an open, link-based recruitment strategy prevented tracking platform-specific participation and the number of individuals who viewed the survey link but did not complete it, limiting the ability to calculate response rates. Finally, because data collection occurred online, individuals with limited internet access or digital literacy may be underrepresented, potentially underestimating barriers to AI use in marginalized populations.

Implications for practice, policy, and future directions

The findings carry important implications for healthcare professionals, educators, and policymakers. Pharmacists and physicians should recognize that patients increasingly consult AI chatbots such as ChatGPT for medication advice. This awareness suggests the need to proactively discuss online health information with patients and provide guidance on verifying sources before acting on them. Integrating AI literacy into public health campaigns and school curricula could empower individuals to critically appraise AI-generated advice.

Healthcare regulators in Saudi Arabia, including the Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA) and the Ministry of Health, should consider developing frameworks or guidelines to ensure the responsible use of AI chatbots for health information, aligned with existing digital health governance initiatives under Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 initiative. Collaborations between academic institutions, technology developers, and professional bodies such as the Saudi Society of Clinical Pharmacy could foster AI models that are locally relevant, culturally appropriate, and medically validated.

For practice, ChatGPT and similar tools could be used as adjunct educational resources, especially in pharmacy and medical education, to improve understanding of drug mechanisms and communication skills. However, professional supervision and validation mechanisms are essential to mitigate risks of misinformation.

Future research should include a broader range of age groups and regions across Saudi Arabia to better understand the demographic and cultural influences on ChatGPT adoption. Exploring the perspectives of healthcare professionals, including pharmacists and physicians, could provide valuable insights into how AI tools can be effectively integrated into patient education and clinical communication. Longitudinal studies examining whether the use of ChatGPT affects medication adherence, self-care practices, and interactions with healthcare providers are also warranted. In addition, interventions that enhance digital health literacy, alongside investigations into privacy, data security, and ethical considerations, are crucial for promoting the safe and effective use of AI in healthcare.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the use of ChatGPT for medication-related information is common among the Saudi public, with nearly two-thirds of participants reporting prior use. Most users consulted ChatGPT to understand how to take medications, their mechanisms of action, and potential side effects.

Approximately one-third of users reported modifying their medication behavior after receiving information from ChatGPT. Use of ChatGPT was more common

among older adults, individuals with diploma-level education, those who were employed, unemployed, or retired, and participants living in smaller households. In contrast, individuals working in medical professions, those with lower income, and users of over-the-counter or herbal medications were less likely to use ChatGPT. Speed, ease of use, and free access were the main factors motivating use, whereas preference for consulting healthcare professionals and concerns about information accuracy were the most frequently reported barriers. Trust and satisfaction with ChatGPT's medication-related information were generally moderate, indicating cautious engagement rather than full reliance on the tool.

Overall, the findings highlight the growing role of AI-based tools as sources of medication-related information among the public, emphasizing the importance of ensuring that such information is used appropriately and interpreted cautiously.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The author declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The author declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Ethical approval and consent to participate: Approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, Saudi Arabia [IRB-2025-05-0570].

The author declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No specific funding was received for this study.

Author contributions

Dr. Faten Alhomoud conceptualized and designed the study, developed the data collection instrument, conducted data collection and analysis, interpreted results, and wrote and revised the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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